

Smithsonian Institution Position Description
Smithsonian Libraries and Archives (SLA)
Digital Imaging Specialist
GS-1001-09

INTRODUCTION

The Smithsonian Institution is a diverse museum and research complex dedicated to the increase and diffusion of knowledge. The Smithsonian Libraries and Archives (SLA) provides authoritative information and innovative services for Smithsonian Institution researchers and curators, as well as scholars and the public worldwide, to further their quest for knowledge. SLA also serves as the institutional memory of a unique cultural organization and is responsible for ensuring institutional accountability. Through responsible collection management, preservation and digital technologies, SLA warrants broad and enduring access to the Libraries' and Archives' collections for all users.

The position is located within the digitization program of the Smithsonian Libraries and Archives (SLA), Smithsonian Institution. SLA's digitization program is responsible for creating digital surrogates of SLA analog collections materials as well as the description, management and curation of the resulting digital assets. The program periodically offers digitization services in support of similar activities for other units and partner organizations in compliance with unit mission and priorities. The purpose of this position is to create, describe, share and maintain high quality digital images from the Libraries and Archives collections, and to support and review such activities as performed by others.

Requires periodic donning of nitrile gloves, finger cots and masks. Requires recurring bending, crouching, stooping, stretching and reaching. Must be able to lift up to 45 lbs. on a regular basis.

MAJOR DUTIES AND RESPONSIBILITIES

Digital Image Production (60%)

Reviews SLA analog collections items selected for digitization to determine appropriate equipment and digitization approach given item condition, format, size and end use case. Coordinates and consults with conservators, following protocols. Independently performs image capture for a variety of bound or loose cultural heritage materials using various specialized equipment and software. Independently performs quality assurance activities through the inspection of new digital surrogates for compliance with SLA standards and makes recommendations for re-imaging or re-processing of legacy digital assets to conform to current practices and standards. Uploads resulting image files into the appropriate system of record for digital asset management, following SLA procedures, and ensures derivative files are made according to established guidelines. Independently completes digitization assignments with specialized requirements for capture and/or processing to meet client needs, such as for exhibition or publication. Engages in direct communication with internal and external

stakeholders to facilitate such requests and provides expert guidance for such projects, which may include digitization of similar materials from other Smithsonian units. Ensures the security and safety of collections items by following policies on proper handling and environmental requirements before, during and after imaging.

Maintains equipment, calibration, color profiles and other digitization configuration factors in accordance with schedule and specifications. Responsible for troubleshooting equipment and software issues. Communicates with internal and external experts for assistance with novel problems when they arise. Alerts supervisor to current and anticipated problems with equipment, accessories or software. Monitors digitization equipment and accessories for wear. Maintains digitization accessories and recommends such items for replacement. Keeps dedicated digital imaging labs and any temporary or permanent designated digital imaging spaces are clean and organized. Supports planning for equipment replacement and lifecycle management, maintaining awareness of industry technological innovation, and new developments in imaging technologies, practices and standards, especially those applying to cultural heritage digitization.

Metadata Generation and Enhancement (25%)

Independently reviews existing descriptive metadata for SLA analog collections items selected for digitization to ensure minimum standards are met. Coordinates with catalogers and metadata specialists for any corrections or enhancement needed prior to digitization. Ensures that image-level (file level) descriptive, administrative and structural metadata are created and applied to digital image files within the system of record, post-production, following Unit standards.

Reviews digital asset metadata application work of self and others, including for preexisting digital assets and/or vendor or rights-holder-supplied digital files, for standards compliance and applies corrections as needed. Independently applies metadata enhancements as part of specialized projects focused on increasing the accessibility and discoverability of digital assets. Such enhancements may include providing metadata for more granular levels of the digital surrogate, for example descriptive information for specific pages/files within a compound digital object, such as individual illustrations or articles within books, or a specific letter within an archival folder. Such enhancements may require consultation with authority files and other specialist resources. Adds digital surrogates to defined collections within systems of record to aid discoverability and access.

Programmatic Support Services (14%)

Organizes workflow to maximize production and meet deadlines for digital image creation, digital asset upload, metadata application and analog material movement. Adheres to digitization workflow requirements, making adjustments for special circumstances. Monitors user requests for digital imaging services and/or metadata services and ensures that requests are completed in a timely manner. Ensures that users are notified when their requests are complete and in any cases of unusual delay or if a request cannot be fulfilled. Maintains relevancy and accuracy of user request queues, editing requests for clarity and removing or

closing any requests that are no longer active. Provides coordination support for agile prioritization of collections materials in the assigned digitization queue.

Supports selection activities through participation in Unit committees and working groups. Serves as point of contact for digitization projects requiring the image production and metadata application of a specific set of collections materials and for specialty digitization requests. Regularly communicates with staff points of contact related to dependent workflows and services such as for preservation review or conservation treatments as well as for descriptive metadata corrections or enhancements for analog materials prior to imaging, and monitors progress on projects and requests. Compiles statistics for digitization projects in addition to those for individual work. Maintains knowledge of and supports the maintenance of documentation for legacy digital assets. Supports inventory or audit processes for such assets. Supports the creation and maintenance of workflow and policy documentation for activities of the SLA digitization program. Takes an active role in updating and maintaining documentation following any changes associated with digitization processes and equipment in collaboration with colleagues. Creates documentation in collaboration with the supervisor. Contributes to and/or authors informational documents for the public and specialists alike, in support of raising awareness of the collections and services of the Unit. Such documents may include blog posts, social media contributions, marketing materials, presentations and/or formal publications. Provides expert guidance for lower graded staff on imaging approaches for collections materials, routine metadata application concerns and workflow processes. Provides oversight to volunteers and interns in digitization and post-production services. Supports creation of statements of work (SOW) and serves as technical point of contact (TPOC) for service contracts. Serves as a representative of the SLA digitization program at meetings and conferences.

Performs other duties as assigned (1%).

FACTOR DESCRIPTIONS

Factor 1 – Knowledge Required by the Position

Work requires skill in applying analytical and evaluative techniques to the identification, consideration and resolution of issues with the digital collection and digitization efforts. Problems within purview typically present themselves during operations or are reported by another party. Must be able to create, interpret and explain written guidelines covering work methods and procedures such as performance and production standards and information on the collections, scanning equipment, metadata specs, project status and ways that work could be performed to bring about more favorable results. Camera work requires familiarity with the camera equipment used in assignments to produce acceptable work. Equipment used is specialized and work requires understanding the uses of a wide range of special purpose accessories, including different types of lenses and lighting sources.

Factor 2 – Supervisory Controls

The incumbent completes assigned digitization projects, stated in terms of goals to be accomplished, and deadlines by which to accomplish them. Where multiple projects are involved, the supervisor may specify priorities among them as well as deadlines for the attainment of specific milestones within each. The supervisor or more senior staff helps on more challenging issues or on the application of advanced analytical methods to measure workload, progress in completing work or forecasting the conclusion to a specific project or project milestone. The incumbent plans, coordinates and carries out successive steps necessary to complete each phase of digitization projects. The incumbent typically resolves recurring and expected problems without consultation of other staff or the supervisor by using established protocols and solid analytical acumen. Work is reviewed for conformance to overall requirements as well as contribution to SLA mission and goals. Final work products are reviewed for consistency, choice of appropriate analytical methods and usability. The incumbent's findings and recommendations are reviewed prior to scoping and further discussion regarding implementation.

Factor 3 – Guidelines

Guidelines consist of standard reference material and procedures covering the completion of digitization assignments and instructions and manuals covering either the technical areas of the records to be created (*e.g.*, art, history, culture, science) and the equipment to be used. Guidelines include thesauri, dictionaries, cataloging rules and formats, authorities lists, literature in the specialized subject area, national and/or international information standards and unit and agency policies and regulations. Methods contained in the established guidance are not always directly applicable to specific work assignments but use cases are directly related and easily adapted. The incumbent uses judgment in choosing, interpreting and adapting available metadata, tagging and pagination guidelines to specific issues or subjects under review. The incumbent must adapt equipment to compensate for physical limitations, care and handling specifications for the format and condition of subject material to generate faithful digital reproductions. Subject material may include bound and loose items, scrapbooks, glass plate negatives, nitrate film and lantern slides. Analyzes the subject and the current guidelines which cover the task at hand (*e.g.*, workflow, delegations of authority or regulatory compliance) and makes recommendations for changes. Correct performance of this work requires independent research of a wide variety of procedural guidelines and applying them with competing interests in mind, such as efficiency, program effectiveness and overall productivity.

Factor 4 – Complexity

Assignments typically involve a variety of still photography. The subjects to be photographed are specified, the extent of coverage is predetermined and the general format is established. Day-to-day work involves taking clear photographs to document objects, documents and images for SLA's digitization operations. The incumbent has discretion to determine the positioning, background, lighting, angles, distance and other aspects that will complement or enhance the subjects based on the intended use and audience for each image. Assignments require the use of different cameras, lenses, lens settings, lighting

equipment and other accessories to produce images of acceptable quality. The incumbent identifies features that are difficult to photograph, such as reflective surfaces, fine or subsurface details, confined spaces or moving parts or that pose processing problems. The incumbent makes compensating adjustments in equipment and techniques. The metadata work involves familiarity with Unit standards and applying that knowledge to a course of action by selecting from many alternatives, including identifying and recommending minor deviations from established practices of the Unit.

Factor 5 – Scope and Effect

This position improves the efficiency and productivity of SLA and its digital assets. The incumbent identifies, analyzes and makes recommendations to resolve conventional problems and situations in workflow, work distribution, staffing, organizational structure and administration of digitization efforts. Collaborates with peers across SI and in industry to promote the highest rate of success in SLA and in the profession. Develops detailed procedures and guidelines to supplement established administrative regulations or program guidance, which are provided to lower-graded staff and contractors, or are used for solicitation of contract services. Completed work products influence SLA decisions concerning internal administrative operations.

Factor 6 – Personal Contacts

Contacts are typically with SI employees, supervisors and managers as well as those from federal agencies or non-federal organizations, both within the US and globally, with similar digital asset and digital imaging functions as part of SLA's participation in consortiums, projects, and other collaborative initiatives. Some contacts are with contract staff working collaboratively or under the incumbent's direction.

Factor 7 – Purpose of Contacts

Contacts are to provide advice to SLA and other managers on noncontroversial image digitization-related issues. The incumbent must identify decision-making alternatives, brief out on success in meeting goals and recommend solutions to persistent problems affecting SLA's digital assets.

Factor 8 – Physical Demands

The work is sometimes sedentary but does require long periods of standing or recurring bending, crouching, stooping, stretching and reaching. Must lift items up to 45 lbs. on a regular basis, such as boxes of books or journals, and moderately heavy equipment and materials.

Factor 9 – Work Environment

Work is typically performed in an adequately lit and climate-controlled office.